

CASHLESS POLICY CONUNDRUM: EXAMINING CUSTOMERS' SATISFACTION OF DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS' SERVICES IN SELECTED SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (SMEs) IN LAGOS STATE

Oguh Festus A, Donald Peterson and Uduehi Benson O.

Department of Business Administration, Wellspring University, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria.

Email: Oguh.festus@wellspringuniversity.com

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Abstract: Nigeria's cashless policy, introduced in 2012 by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), aimed to promote a more efficient and secure financial system by encouraging the use of electronic payments. While the policy has achieved some successes, such as reducing the amount of cash in circulation and increasing the use of electronic payments, it has also presented challenges for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). **Objectives:** The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of cashless policy on SME customers' satisfaction in selected (5) five deposit money banks in Lagos State. **Methods:** This study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design. Inferential statistics was used to examine the relationship between the variables under investigation. **Results:** The result shows that Cashless policy practices have positive and moderately average relationship with SMEs' customer satisfaction of deposit money banks in Lagos State ($R = 0.68, p=0.000$) **Conclusion:** This study assert and accepts that Cashless policy practices (Debit and credit cards, online bank transfers) do significantly affect SMEs' customer satisfaction of deposit money banks in Lagos State. **Recommendations:** Banks should address the issue of customer education by embarking on rigorous campaigns to educate customers on how to use various payments platforms; Banks should invest in digital infrastructure that can handle increased digital transactions real- time that are user friendly, secure and reliable.

Keywords: SMEs, Cashless Policy, E-Cash, Credit Card, Online Bank Transfer.

Introduction

Nigeria's cashless policy, introduced in 2012 by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), aimed to promote a more efficient and secure financial system by encouraging the use of electronic payments. While the policy has achieved some successes, such as reducing the amount of cash in circulation and increasing the use of electronic payments, it has also presented challenges for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). These challenges can negatively impact SME customer satisfaction. For example, if a customer cannot pay for a product or service electronically, they may take their business elsewhere. Additionally, if an SME makes a mistake using electronic payments, it can damage their reputation and lead to lost customers. These are clear examples of confusion which the policy tends to cause with adverse effect on SMEs customer satisfaction.

Cashless policy is a policy where there are other payment options like debit and credit cards, bank transfers, bank direct debits, Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), and even mobile money (CBN 2023). The cashless policy adopted in Nigeria was aimed at scaling up financial inclusion and reducing crimes through the financial system such as armed robbery, kidnapping, terrorism financing, advance fee fraud, graft, ransom payment, extortion and

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other crimes. It increases the volume of all available payment's channels in the country, as well as promote end-to-end electronic payments in Nigeria and diaspora. Despite the policy's prominent goals, it remains a topical issue of debate in the country as it affects its implementation. The rate of rapid development at global level has been so dynamic that it touches all aspects of human venture (Latifat & Alhassan 2015). Policymakers and development practitioners acknowledge the leading role of information and communication technologies (ICTs) for development (Dutta & Mia, 2009). Today, the world is now a global village, given the growing complexity of business portfolios and expansion of business groups, and the increase in decentralization in response to these changes (Tasmin, Abubakar & Josu, 2012). Thus, cashless policy services have been gaining ground around the globe. This offers banking industry a new leading edge of opportunities and challenges in the global banking market. Hence, the success of cashless economy services depends on the rate at which customers adopt the new technology.

. In view of the above, this study examines the influence of cashless transactions on SME customer satisfaction within the scope of (5) five selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Introduction of withdrawal limits announced by CBN regarding cash withdrawal policy across all payment channels by individuals and corporate organizations effective January 9, 2023, caused serious financial crisis as individuals and corporate entities could only withdraw a maximum of N500,000.00 and N5 million respectively on weekly basis compared to N100,000.00 and N500,000.00 which was previously announced on December 6, 2022. The new policy on cash-based transactions which seeks to reduce the amount of physical cash circulating in the economy, and not to eliminate it as well as to encourage more electronic-based transactions in the payments for goods, and services among others almost crippled the Nigeria economy.

In Nigeria, customers of banks seek for safety of their funds and increased returns on their investment. Customers demand efficient, fast and convenient services. Many customers today want banks that offer them services that will meet their particular needs and support their business goals. For instance, a business man wants to travel without carrying cash for security reasons. The central bank of Nigeria has emphasized the need for banks to provide more efficient services to their existing and potentials customers (Latifat & Alhassan 2015).

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of cashless policy on SME customers' satisfaction in selected (5) five Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Evaluate the influence of e-cash on SME customers' satisfaction in the selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State.
- ii. Assess the influence of online credit card payment system on SME customers' satisfaction of the selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State.

Research Questions

- i. To what extent does the influence of e-cash affect SME customers' satisfaction of the selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State?
- ii. What is the impact of online credit card payment system on SME customer' satisfaction of the selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and strengthen the analysis.

Hypothesis one

H1: E-cash do not significantly influence SME customers' satisfaction of Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State

Hypothesis two

H2: Online credit card payment system do not significantly influence SME customers' satisfaction of Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Concept of cashless policy

A policy that discourages the use of huge raw cash for transactions but encourages the use of bank transfer, ATM card, POS, and other financial instruments for financial transactions. Cashless economy does not mean an outright elimination of cash transactions in the economic setting but one in which the amount of cash-based transactions are kept to the barest minimum. According to Woodford (2003), cashless economy is defined as one in which there are assumed to be no transactions frictions that can be reduced through the use of money balances, and that accordingly provide a reason for holding such balances even when they earn rate of return. The following among others enhance the functioning of cashless economy; e-finance, e-banking, e-money, e-brokering, e-exchanges etc. In a modern economy, the use of noncash payment methods such as cards (credit and debit) dominates the use of cash in payments (Acha, 2008a).

The cashless policy initiative of the Central Bank of Nigeria is a move to improve the financial terrain of the economy. The policy aims at reducing (not eliminating) the amount of physical cash (coins and notes) circulating in the economy, and to encourage more electronic-based transactions (payments for goods, services, transfers). A cashless society is a culture where no one uses cash, all purchases being made are by credit cards, charge cards, cheques, or direct transfers from one account to another through mobile banking or other electronic money transfer modes. The cashless society refers to the widespread application of computer technology in the financial system (Obi, 2011). Considering the success potential of this policy Ejiro (2012) opined that "in the long run sustainability of the policy will be a function of the endorsement of, and compliance by end-users". According to Central Bank of Nigeria (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2011) the policy is expected to reduce cost incurred in maintaining cash-based economy by 90% upon its full implementation.

The cashless initiative is an alternative to cash transactions through electronic means using information and communications technology (ICT). Ndifon and Okpa (2014) maintain that the future of all business, particularly those in the service industry lies in information technology. This technology as far as cashless policy is concerned is not only computer. Information technology for banks takes different forms; computerization of customers' accounts and account information storage and retrieval; deposit and withdrawal through Automated Teller Machines (ATMs); and networking to facilitate access to accounts from any branch of the bank, bio-metrics, use of mobile phones to consummate transactions, internet, and websites. It also involves the use of credit cards, debit

cards, mobile pay and many other forms of payment, but always only in digital ways, as paper currency does not come into play.

Concept of Online Credit Card Payment System

Online credit card payment system is a payment card issued to users (cardholders) to enable the cardholder to pay a merchant for goods and services based on the cardholder's promise to the card issuer to pay them for the amounts plus the other agreed charges. The card issuer (usually a bank) creates a revolving account and grants a line of credit to the cardholder, from which the cardholder can borrow money for payment to a merchant or as a cash advance (Birch and Young, 2017). A credit card is different from a charge card, which requires the balance to be repaid in full each month. In contrast, credit cards allow the consumers to build a continuing balance of debt, subject to interest being charged.

A credit card also differs from a cash card, which can be used like currency by the owner of the card. A credit card differs from a charge card also in that a credit card typically involves a third-party entity that pays the seller and is reimbursed by the buyer, whereas a charge card simply defers payment by the buyer until a later date. It seeks to extend the functionality of existing credit cards for use as online shopping payment tools. This payment system has been widely accepted by consumers and merchants throughout the world, and by far the most popular methods of payments especially in the retail markets (Laudon & Traver, 2012). This form of payment system has several advantages, which were never available through the traditional modes of payment. Some of the most important are: privacy, integrity, compatibility, good transaction efficiency, acceptability, convenience, mobility, low financial risk and anonymity. Added to all these, to avoid the complexity associated with the digital cash or electronic-cheques, consumers and vendors are also looking at credit card payments on the internet as one of possible time-tested alternative. But, this payment system has raised several problems before the consumers and merchants.

Online credit card payment seeks to address several limitations of online credit card payments for merchant including lack of authentication, repudiation of charges and credit card frauds. It also seeks to address consumer fears about using credit card such as having to reveal credit information at multiple sites and repeatedly having to communicate sensitive information over the internet. Basic process of online credit card payment system is very simple. If consumers want to purchase a product or service, they simply send their credit card details.

Concept of Electronic Cash Payment System

Electronic cash (e-cash) is a new concept in online payment system because it combines computerized convenience with security and privacy that improve on paper cash. Its versatility opens up a host of new markets and applications. E-cash is an electronic or digital form of value storage and value exchange that have limited convertibility into other forms of value and require intermediaries to convert. E-cash presents some characteristics like monetary value, storability and irretrievability, interoperability and security. All these characteristics made it more attractive payment system over the Internet.

Additionally, this payment system offers numerous advantages like authority, privacy, good acceptability, low transactions cost, convenience and good anonymity. But, this system of payment also have many limitations like poor mobility, poor transaction efficiency and high financial risk, as people are solely responsible for the lost or stolen. Gary and Perry (2012), just like real world currency counterpart, electronic cash is susceptible to forgery. It is possible, though increasingly difficult, to create and spend forged e-cash.

E-cash structure: e-cash structure could be identified as a string of bits that represents certain values such as reference number and digital signature, which could be used for the security purpose to prevent forgery and criminal use (Wright, 2012). But, the structure proposed by Wright (2012) needs some extension to make e-cash more secure. Therefore, the present model adds a digital watermark to e-cash structure to protect it from the illegal copy and forgery activities further, the model modified the structure of the reference number to support tractability.

The proposed e-cash structure is comparatively better than suggested by Wright (2012), because security issue is given importance of top most priority in the present model. But, still there are certain concerns to be addressed for an electronic cash system. For example, who has the right to issue electronic cash? Can every bank issue its own money? If so how do you prevent fraud? And who will monitor the banking operations to protect consumers? Many of these concepts relate to the legal and banking regulatory aspects. However, all these issues are beyond the scope of the study and therefore, cannot be included here. But, these issues must be addressed before establishing a complete e-cash based payment system.

Concept of Automated Teller Machine System

Automated Teller Machine (ATM) has been defined by Abubakar and Tosmin (2012) as a computerized telecommunications device that provide the customers of a financial institution with access to financial transactions in a public space without the need of a human clerk or bank teller. Ali and Emenike (2016) perceive it as a computerized telecommunication's device that provide clients of a financial institution with access to financial transactions in a public space without the need for a cashier, human clerk or bank teller. Fenuga (2010) states that it is a machine where cash withdrawals are made over the machine without going into the banking hall. According to him, it also sells recharge cards of all networks as well as make transfers across all banks; it can be accessed 24 hours/7 days with account balance enquiries. Ogbuji *et al.* (2012) noted that ATM allows a bank customer to conduct his/her banking transactions from almost every other ATM machine in the world.

An ATM is an electronic device which can be used to carry out bank transactions. Some of the services offered by an ATM include withdrawal of funds, account balance inquiry, transfer of funds, and top-up on airtime for mobile phones etc. An ATM is operated with an electronic card. Each card has a Personal Information Number (PIN) which gives access to the account of the owner of the card. The first ATM that was offered to the public was in 1969 at the chemical bank in Rockville Center, New York. ATM'S were introduced into Nigeria in the year 1989. It was installed by national cash registers (NCR) for the society General Bank of Nigeria.

Ayo, Adewoye and Oni (2011) posit that banking industry can no longer get away with operating loosely connected groups of businesses that happen to be located around the world, but must tactically synchronize their operations to suit their clients or customers. They maintained further that it is only the banks, businesses, industries and any other segment of the community that clearly understand the new rules of doing business in a global business economy that will succeed. In view of this, global competition in the banking sector has compelled management and executives to recognize that they must think differently about banking and management operations, especially of the MSMEs. Today, ATMs are not placed only in the banks or inside their premises but also in locations such as shopping malls, airports, grocery stores, petrol/gas stations, restaurants, cinema.

Concept of SME customer Satisfaction

SME customer satisfaction is defined as a collection of outcome of perception, evaluation and psychological reactions to the consumption experience with a product/service (Wright and Ralson (2012). In other words, Wright and Ralson further define SME customer satisfaction as a result of a cognitive and affective evaluation where some comparison standard is compared to the actually perceived performance. SME customer's satisfaction holds the potential for increasing an organization's SME customer base, increase the use of more volatile SME customer mix and increase the firm's reputation (Alabar, 2012). According to Ikechukwu (2010), consumer satisfaction is a term frequently used in marketing is a measure of how products and services supplied by a company meet or surpasses SME customer expectation. He added that SME customer satisfaction is the number of SME customers, or percentage of total SME customers, whose reported experience with a firm, its products, or its services (ratings) exceeds specified satisfaction goals.

Satisfaction is a judgment that follows a consumption experience - it is the consumer's judgment that a product provided (or is providing) a pleasurable level of consumption-related fulfillment (Nwaze, 2019). During consumption, SME customers experience the product performance and compare it to their expected product performance level. Satisfaction judgments are then formed based on this comparison. The resulting judgment is labelled positively if the performance is better than expected, negative disconfirmation if it is worse than expected and simple confirmation if it is as expected. In short, SME customers evaluate product performance by comparing what they expected with what they believe they received.

Consumer satisfaction is seen as a key performance indicator within business and is often part of a Balanced Scorecard. In a competitive marketplace where businesses compete for SME customers, SME customer satisfaction is seen as a key differentiator and increasingly has become a key element of business strategy within organizations; SME customer satisfaction ratings can have powerful effects. They focus on employees and the importance of fulfilling SME customers' expectations. Furthermore, when these ratings dip, these problems can affect sales and profitability. When a brand has loyal SME customers, it gains positive word-of-mouth marketing, which is both free and highly effective. In researching satisfaction, firms generally ask SME customers whether their product or service has met or exceeded expectations. Thus, expectations are a key factor behind satisfaction. When consumers have high expectations and the reality falls they will be disappointed and will likely rate their

experience as less than satisfying. Conventional managerial wisdom holds that attending to SME customer satisfaction, value, and loyalty makes good business sense for at least two reasons:

- a. Satisfied SME customers are likely to continue to buy from and/or continue to do business with a company, while dissatisfied SME customers are likely to take their business elsewhere.
- b. Satisfied SME customers tell others about their positive experiences, while dissatisfied SME customers tell even more people about their negative experiences.

Today's most successful companies are raising expectations and delivering performance to match, these companies embrace total SME customer satisfaction. They track their SME customers' expectations, perceived company's performance and SME customer satisfaction. A company can always increase SME customer satisfaction by lowering its price or increasing its services but this may result in lower profits. Thus, the purpose of marketing is to generate SME customer value profitability and this requires a very delicate balance. The marketer must continue to generate more SME customer value and satisfaction but not "give away the house, clubs, hotels, churches, mosques, train and bus stations and any such place large enough for people to gather and carry out different kinds of transactions (Hazlina et al, 2011). ATM services have become a great facilitator of quick small cash withdrawals and transfers and it has brought a lot of ease in business operations, especially for the small businesses in Nigeria.

Technological Acceptance Model

The theory of technological acceptance model which was propounded by Fred Davis in 1993 explains how individuals accept new technology and it leads to growth in an economy. In essence, it shows how a user of a proposed technology welcomes and adapts to a new technology. According to Davis (1993), two beliefs determine the complete acceptance of a technology. These beliefs are perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Perceived Usefulness is a factor that affects user's acceptance because it is based on how capable the new technology will help improve job performance.

The technology must be capable of producing an advantageous result and must also be able to generate a positive performance. As for perceived Ease of Use, Fred Davis defined it as how easy it is for users to make use of new technology. It means that the ability to employ the new technology should be effortless. Prior to the implementation of the cashless policy, Nigeria was a huge cash-based economy. In order to increase the effect of the policy on citizens, the people have to believe that the policy will be easy to use and also result in positive performance thereby, leading to economic growth. E-Banking products must also be reengineered to make electronic payment effortless which will stir the country toward a cashless economy (Nwankwo & Eze, 2013).

Empirical Review

Various studies on cashless policy and electronic payments and banking have been carried out since the inception of the policy. Fenug and Kolade (2010) investigated the effect of electronic payment on customer service delivery, as brought about by problem of satisfying customers need in Nigerian banks. The study was conducted on four commercial banks (United Bank for Africa, First bank, Zenith bank and Intercontinental bank) in Nigeria. The

survey design was used for the study, which focused on the population of the four selected commercial banks in Nigeria. One hundred respondents were stratified proportionately amongst customers of the selected banks with the aid of questionnaire randomly administered. Chi-square and regression analysis were employed in testing whether there is significant relationship between the level of automation banking services and improvement in delivery of services to their numerous customers in Nigeria. The study concludes that electronic payment has significant impact on the services render by the banking industry in Nigeria thereby improves customer service delivery, better management efficiency, increased profit, customer satisfaction and sustainability in Nigeria.

Akpan, (2016) investigated on the influence of ATM service quality on customer satisfaction in the banking sector of Nigeria. The study adopted survey research in which questionnaires were administered on customers of four banks randomly selected for the study (First Bank of Nigeria Plc., United Bank for Africa Plc., Guarantee Trust Bank Plc. and Skye Bank Plc.) at the ATMs terminals of the Banks during transactions. Multiple Regression Analysis, Descriptive Statistics of the Mean, Standard Deviation, Tables and Charts were the main tools of data analysis. Findings revealed that the higher the ATM service quality, the higher the level of satisfaction it provides. The study then concluded that ATM service quality determines customer satisfaction. The study recommended that banks should improve on their service quality for them to remain relevant in the face of global competition.

Simon and Senaji (2016) investigated on effect of electronic banking on customer satisfaction in selected commercial banks, domiciled in Kenya. The general aim of the study was to determine the effect of electronic banking and customer satisfaction among first tier bank in Nairobi Town. The study was hinged on diffusion innovation theory and contrast theory. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The target population was 262,511 customers drawn from 5 first tier banks within Nairobi CBD. Stratified sampling technique was used to select a sample size 225 respondents. Primary data was collected using structured questionnaires addressed to the participants. The study conducted a regression analysis to establish the relationship between the study variables. From the findings, the study concluded that flexibility of internet banking influence customer satisfaction to a great extent. The study further concluded that usefulness of internet banking and friendliness of internet banking has relatively low effect on customer satisfaction. The study recommended that Management of banking institutions should enhance application of mobile banking to increase satisfaction of their customers. Mobile service providers in conjunction with banks should develop more friendly and easy to use and efficient applications for bank customers.

Onobrakpeya and Mac-Attama (2017) investigated on improving customer satisfaction through digital marketing in the Nigerian deposit money banks. The objective of the study was to ascertain the effect of digital marketing on customer satisfaction in the Nigerian deposit's money banks. The study made use of a sample of 214 employees from some selected banks in Warri Metropolis in Delta State, Nigeria. Cross sectional survey research design method was adopted, and the statistical techniques used comprised of simple percentage, correlation and multiple regression analysis. Findings showed that e-mail marketing have the highest significant positive effect on customer satisfaction in the Nigerian deposit money banks. The implication is that customers appreciate regular

communication via e-mail because it brings value and satisfaction to them. The study concluded that companies whose website have quality contents are ranked higher in search engine results and are better positioned in achieving superior performance by way of customer satisfaction. The study recommended that a strategy should be put in place to integrate mobile marketing with other digital marketing media during its implementation because it is difficult to separate customers from their mobile devices and gadget.

Amin, Onyeukwu and Osuagwu (2018) investigated on E – banking, service quality and customer satisfaction in selected Nigerian banks. This study examined the relationship between the quality of service and customer satisfaction in the e-banking era. A sample of 398 respondents was selected, out of the total number of 66,895 customer population. Structured questionnaires and interview were used in collecting the data. Descriptive statistics was adopted in analyzing the data from the respondents. The results revealed that there is a significant relationship between quality of service and customer satisfaction. The study concluded that E-banking has a positive impact on the quality of service in the Nigerian banking sector, but not on customer satisfaction. The study recommended that staff training and development should be enhanced in the banking industry in order to render quality and timely services to their customers.

Conceptual Framework

Source: Developed by the Researcher (2024) after extensive review of literature.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is survey research design. Survey research design was used because the study attempted to describe and explain conditions of the study by using questionnaires to ascertain the relationship between cashless policy and customer satisfaction of selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos. This design involves the use of sample to obtain the opinion of number of respondents. It is a research design that studies the information gathered from a fraction or percentage of the population.

The study area of this study was the branches of the (5) selected Deposit Money Banks in Lagos state.

The population of this study consisted of customers of the big five Deposit Money Banks (FUGAZ) branches as it relates to customer satisfaction in Alimosho LGA, Lagos state. Alimosho was used for the study for its market share and customer base.

The Cochran (1997) formula of sample size determination was used to compute the sample size for this study. The Cochran (1997) sample size formula is appropriate being a scientific method to determine sample size from a known population.

$$n = \frac{NZ^2pq}{d^2(N-1) + Z^2pq}$$

Where:

n = sample size,

N = population size (total number of customer/banks branches),

Z = 95% Confidence Interval (Z = 1.96)

p = 0.5

q = 1-p

d = degree of estimation (0.05)

Applying the formula;

$$n = \frac{8396 \times (1.96)^2 \times 0.5 \times (1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2 \times (8396-1) + (1.96)^2 \times 0.5 \times (1-0.5)}$$
$$= \frac{8063.5184}{21.9479}$$

$$n = 367.39$$

$$= 367$$

The purposive sampling was used in selecting the five banks under study. The respondents consisted of customers of each bank under study.

Inferential Statistics

Regression and correlation analysis was used to test the stated hypotheses. The stated hypotheses on relationships between the independent and the dependent were tested using correlation analysis while regression analysis was used to determine the contribution of the independent variables on the dependent variables.

a. Regression analysis

Regression analysis were used to ascertain the extent of changes in the value of the dependent variables as a result of changes in the set of the predictor variables. It helped to determine how the values of the outcomes variables would change when anyone of the independent variables is varied while the others are held constant. Thus, this would help to reveal which of the independent variables is more significantly related to the dependent variables.

To test whether the coefficient of determination (R^2) is statistically significant or not, the *sig.* value also known as *p-value* of the result is compared with the level of significance used for the study. A low *p-value* (<0.05) indicates the independent variable is significant; therefore, null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted. Conversely, a larger *p-value* (>0.05) indicates that the independent variable is insignificant, therefore, null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is rejected (Ibrahim, 2016; Abdul-Hafix, 2012).

b. Correlation analysis

Correlation analysis is used to ascertain the nature, direction and strength of the relationship between variable. The Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient (r) is assessed in determining the association in question. To test whether the correlation coefficient (r) is statistically significant or not, the *sig.* value also known as *p-value* of the result is compared with the level of significance used for the study. A low *p-value* (<0.05) indicates the independent variable is significant; therefore, null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted. Conversely, a larger *p-value* (>0.05) indicates that the independent variable is insignificant, therefore, null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is rejected (Ibrahim, 2016; Abdul-Hafix, 2012).

The Decision Rule: Accept H_0 and reject H_1 if $P\text{-value} \geq 0.05$

The data obtained were processed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 23 software. It offers advance statistical and text analysis, integrates with big data, open source extensibility. This software is flexible, scalable, accessible, and easy to use and supports hypothesis testing. The processed data was subsequently analyzed using both descriptive (tables, graphs, percentages, means and standard deviation) and inferential statistics specifically ordinary least squares regression at 5% level of significant.

3 Model Specification

The independent variable for the study which is cashless policy was measured by Debit and Credit, Online bank transfers

On the other hand, Customer satisfaction is the dependent variable. Mathematically, CS is a function of cashless policy.

$$Y = f(X_i)$$

Y = Dependent variable = Customer Satisfaction (CS)

X = Independent variable = Cashless Policy (CP)

$$CS = f(CP)$$

Since CP = DC, OLBT,.

Therefore, $CS = f(dc, olbt)$.

$$Y = X_i$$

$$X_i = X_1, X_2,$$

Where

Y = SME Customer Satisfaction (CS)

X = Cashless policy (CP)

The indicators of Cashless Policies (X) are;

X₁ = e-cash

X₂ = Online credit card payment system (occps)

The simple regression equations for each hypothesis are:

Hypothesis one

H0: E-cash system do not significantly influence SME customer satisfaction of deposit money banks in Lagos State

$$Y = a_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + e_i$$

$$CS = a_0 + \beta_1 \text{ e-cash} + e_i \dots \dots \dots \text{Model I}$$

Hypothesis two

H0: Online credit card payment system do not significantly influence customer satisfaction of deposit money banks in Lagos State

$$Y = a_0 + \beta_2 X_2 + e_i$$

$$CS = a_0 + \beta_2 \text{ occps} + e_i \dots \dots \dots \text{Model 2}$$

Results

Multiple regression analysis

Hypothesis

Cashless policy practices (Debit and credit cards, Online bank transfers) do not significantly affect SME customer satisfaction of Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State.

Independent variables

X₁ = Debit and credit cards

X₂ = Online bank transfers

Dependent variable

Y = Customer satisfaction

Multiple regression analysis was used to test these hypotheses. Table 4.12 presents the model fit, which establishes how the model equation fits the data and Adjusted R-square (Adj. R²), used to establish the predictive power of the study’s model. The table further presents the coefficients of the identified Cashless policy practices.

Summary of multiple regression analysis for the effect of Cashless policy practices on customer satisfaction of Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State

Model	Beta	t	Sig.	R	R ²	Adj. R ²	ANOVA Sig.	F(df)
(Constant)	0.43	4.51	0.00	0.68	0.462	0.459	0.000	149.27 (4,241)

Debit and credit cards	0.12	3.27	0.00
Online bank transfers	0.26	7.65	0.00

Source: Computed by the Researcher (2024)

The result shows that Cashless policy practices have positive and moderately average relationship with SME customer satisfaction of deposit money banks in Lagos State ($R = 0.68, p=0.000$). The adjusted coefficient of determination ($Adj R^2$) of 0.459 showed that cashless policy practices explained 45.9% of the variation in SME customer satisfaction of deposit money banks in Lagos State while the remaining 54.1% variation in customer satisfaction of deposit money banks in Lagos; is explained by other exogenous variable different from those considered in this study.

Furthermore, the table presents the results of ANOVA (overall model significance) of regression test which revealed that the cashless policy practices have a significant effect on customer satisfaction of deposit money banks in Lagos State. These can be explained by the F-value (149.27) and p-value (0.000) which is statistically significant at 95% confidence interval.

The results of regression coefficients for cashless policy practices in relation to customer satisfaction of deposit money banks in Lagos State revealed that at 95% confidence level, debit and credit cards ($\beta = 0.12, p= 0.000$), Online bank transfers ($\beta = 0.26, p= 0.000$), Based on the coefficients of regression in table, the regression model is restated as follows:

$$CS = 0.43 + 0.12 DC + 0.26 ONLBT + \dots \dots \dots \text{Eq. (i)}$$

Where: DC = Debit and credit cards

ONLBT = Online bank transfers

According to the regression equation above, considering all factors, customer satisfaction is 0.12. The result also indicates that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit change in Debit and credit cards will lead to a 0.12 increase in customer satisfaction. Online bank transfers will also lead to a 0.26 increase in customer satisfaction given that all other factors are considered

Given these results, this study can conclude that cashless policy practices significantly affect customer satisfaction of Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State. On the strength of this result ($Adj R^2= 0.459, F (4,241) = 149.27, p= 0.000$); this study rejects that Cashless policy practices (Debit and credit cards, online bank transfers, do not significantly affect SME customer satisfaction of Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State.

Conclusion: This study asserts and accepts that Cashless policy practices (Debit and credit cards, online bank transfers) do significantly affect SME customer satisfaction of Deposit Money Banks in Lagos State. The Challenges Faced by SMEs include: Limited access to technology: Many SMEs, particularly in rural areas, lack access to the technology needed to use electronic payments. This can include issues such as lack of internet access, reliable electricity, and affordable smartphones; Financial literacy: Some SME owners and employees were not familiar with how to use electronic payments, which can lead to confusion and errors; Transaction

costs: Some electronic payment platforms charge merchants transaction fees, which can eat into SMEs' profits; Resistance to change: Some customers, particularly older generations, may be resistant to using electronic payments and prefer to pay with cash.

These challenges negatively impact on SME customer satisfaction. For example, the SME customer who cannot pay for a product or service electronically, they were made to take their business elsewhere. Additionally, if an SME customer makes a mistake using electronic payments, it can damage their reputation and lead to lost customers.

Recommendations

Since banking business is all about customers, convenience for customers should also be paramount in the minds of banks as customers increasingly prefer the convenience and ease of digital transactions providing customers with seamless and trouble free banking experience.

Banks should also continue to address the issue of customer education by embarking on rigorous campaigns to educate customers on how to use various payments platforms and the benefit accrued; Investment in digital infrastructure that can handle increased digital transaction real time that are user friendly, secure and reliable.

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